

Spotlight: Sea level

Version V1
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Background

Sea level is an essential ocean variable and a key climate change indicator, which integrates the response of several components of the Earth system (ocean, atmosphere, cryosphere and hydrosphere) to both natural and anthropogenic forcing. Sea level rise varies significantly from region to region since it is affected by ocean currents, local water density changes, ice melt fingerprints, and vertical land movements. Observing regional sea-level is crucial, as rising sea levels pose significant risks to coastal populations, infrastructure, and coastal ecosystems. Sea-level observations and projections inform governments in designing resilient coastal protection and adaptation, revising construction codes, enhancing early-warning capabilities, integrating marine spatial planning and guiding communities through long-term adaptation.

The Challenge

Understanding sea level changes is complicated due to its significant regional variability. Long-term and consistent observations are still limited in many regions, such as in the Arctic, where extensive sea-ice cover restricts the ability to maintain and expand observational networks. Challenges also arise from the spatial distribution of satellite observations, which is denser in the tropics than in the Arctic. Another challenge is integrating diverse data sources such as satellites, tide gauges, and Argo floats each characterised by distinct measurement methodologies and calibration protocols.

ObsSea4Clim activities

ObsSea4Clim focuses on four regions: (1) the Arctic Ocean, (2) the Nordic and Barents Seas, (3) the North and Baltic Seas, and (4) the European Shelf. Within these regions, we implement the following activities:

- Review of the observation needs to monitor sea level variability in the Arctic Ocean, the Nordic Seas, and the Barents Sea (study regions 1 and 2), with special focus on sea level budget.
- Investigating the extreme sea level variability in the Arctic and the Nordic Seas (study regions 1 and 2), using climate models (CMIP6).
- Investigating sea level extremes that may be missed by the existing sea level observing systems, such as seiches, and meteotsunamis. So far, we have investigated the observing network in Ireland (study region 4) in relation to a specific extreme sea level event case study (Swan et al., 2026).
- Understanding how ocean currents contribute to extreme events (Diabaté et al., 2025) in study region 4.

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- Combining satellite altimetry and tide gauge observations to reproduce sea level variability with time scales of days. An experimental sea level data set has been produced for the Baltic Sea (study region 3) based on satellite altimetry and tide gauges on a timescale much shorter than a month.

Resources

1. Presentation on future projection of atmospheric and oceanic impacts on sea level at Arctic and near-Arctic coastlines, delivered by Emmanuel Eresanya (NUIM) at the ObsSea4Clim Annual Meeting, March 2025.
Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/15076909>; YouTube: <https://youtu.be/1IAjNu-bqol>

Latest Publications

1. Y. Liu, J. Sun, R.P. Raj et al. (2025) The role of North Pacific teleconnection in the sea level change of the Canadian Basin. *Atmospheric and Oceanic Science Letters*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aosl.2025.100752>.
2. Diabaté, S. T., Fraser, N. J., White, M., Berx, B., Marié, L., & McCarthy, G. D. (2025). On the wind-driven European shelf sea-level variability and the associated oceanic circulation. *Continental Shelf Research*, 291, 105466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2025.105466>
3. Swan, L. D., Bergin, C., McCarthy, G. D. (2026). Investigating a suspected meteotsunami along the Northwest Coast of Ireland in February 2022. *In revision for Natural Hazards*.

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